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Sociological Disclosure on Social Capital through Narratives¹Dr Sonia Rajoria

This article intends to describe the phenomenon of relationship between social capital and family relations between husband and wife along with children and taken consideration its social parameters of Social Capital in the India. The geographical locations have inhibited some similarities as well as differences, like rural or urban, caste, class and status as far as culture, history, and traditions are concerned. The unprecedented changes after Post Covid-19 Paradigm shift the economy, triggered by the phenomenon and the processes of modernization and urbanization, family life has experienced some phenomenal changes, which has led many scholars of social sciences to ruminate over it as profoundly as possible. The present paper in the context has been enumerates by some following objectives; firstly, to gain insight into the comparison of Family Relations between husband and wife along with children and see the various social phenomenon's of social capital through previous Indian Literature Reviews also, collectively take theoretical Framework for fulfill the designated title of the research paper. Second objective is to be acquainted with why the young generation became detached/ disorganized from their families, etc. so we will get the deep insight for that of the particular area to adore it the most presentable situation in India.

Keywords: Social Capital, Family Relations, Husband and Wife, Children.

Introduction

The system of family has undergone qualitative changes because of Industrialization Modernization, education, influence of urbanization, changes in marriage system migration, revolution in the field of transport and communication, increasing influence of the state and the influence of the individualization philosophy of life. Awareness among women has changed the social capital, or the dependence and sustainability among family members. The changes have been so fast in some parts of the world. With the advent of industrial civilization with modern technology the structure and functions of the family fatedly changed.

It is essential to understand that how family relates the social capital and how this term is useful for the family members and as well as in society. Family is particularly considered as a system where the actual interactions among members have constituted the layer of reality and trust in it. Another term social capital is a composition of the family which gives the quality of life within the family relationships which has included the parameters such as trust, family co-relation, solidarity, family participation, family cohesion, etc which they have also strengthen the family relationships in a family. From this point of view the family is an “impulsive

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social subjectivity” along with the extraordinary memories and the identity ^[1].

Therefore, family as a social capital is considered as a characteristic of relationships relatively than entities or structures: it is developing the belongings and to control the abnormal family relations and to engender the dimensions of social capital parameters ^[2].

Couples are the bases of a family association and their relations effects on other aspects of the society. Good Relations between the husband-wife along with their children have good adjustment are deemed as social capital.

Social capital is an important feature in weakening and strengthening family functions. It is a group where the family members can collaborate with each other through non-social and regulating norms. Trust, family co-relation, solidarity, family involvement, family cohesion, etc. are the indicators of the social capital. Hence, if the social capital increases, it will also increase the adjustment between husband-wife and their children relationship then it will cause more ruling and if social capital decreases then it will cause more social divergence, like crime, family destruction, abnormality into the relationships, addition of bad habits, suicide, etc. Generally modernization, industrialization, influence of urbanization, changes in marriage system, influence of modern values have weakens the family social capital^[3].

Classical sociologists were interested in paying the attention into the quality in social relationships within the various types of families which were subjected. In this up-bringing we should keep in mind that Indian families have changed from the traditional form to the new form because of urbanization, globalization, industrial economy, developing of transportation systems, expanding bureaucracy, established educational systems and universities and developed mass media. ^[4]

An Indian family is entirely different from the western unit. It has greater cohesion and greater continuity. Even when sons are forced to get separated from the parental family because of their job, education, etc., their bonds with the parental unit remains unbreakable in most of the cases. The ties among the members remain more tenuous, subtle and slender. But before analyzing that family as a social capital in the metro city Delhi, we must know about the general concepts of the family.

Social Capital

Bourdieu (1977) has initially defined in his first published in 1973 that social capital is ‘Capital of social relationships which will provide, if necessary, useful, supports’: a capital of honorability and respectability which is often indispensable if one desires to attract clients in socially important positions, and which may serve as currency, for instance in a political career”.

Robert Putnam (2000) defines social capital as „connections among individuals– social networks and the norms of reciprocity and trustworthiness that rise from them“. We find the existence of social capital in many families because it gives the quality of life as well as develops the society. The term “Social Capital” is a way of defining the intangible resources of community, shared values and trust upon which is evident in daily life; it is a relationship between human beings.

Riddell, Baron and Wilson (1999) indicated that there have been mainly two frameworks where they have brought the understanding that how social capital arises and their effects on the family. As Riddell, Baron and Wilson (1999: 55) within that of this perspective of social capital „it is the social network of which engage the family relations or the community relations which mainly liable their ability to get engage in education, training and work and also prolonged a healthy civic community or the family

relations.

Coleman's had mainly focused on how an individual's attainment of human capital demonstrated by recognizing the significance level of family and also inter-family relations which develops the Coleman's framework to develop the more account that influences the social structure.

Critical theorists have been concerned about the other things, of which mainly focus on to develop the power relationships. It is the work of Bourdieu (1979, 1986, 1987, and 1989) that has been most influential terms while doing critical analysis in the study of Social Capital. The main base of Bourdieu's work was to express that how social advantage and their disadvantage are based on historically and maintained. He also identified four types of capital these are cultural, social, economic and symbolic. He refers to social capital as a way of connections, to link or to build the relationships and maintain as well as. He suggests that such type of connections is very useful when understanding the society and families is the main point of to build up and broadcast of social capital.

Social capital has some characteristics that are studied:
Family trust:

- Family co-relation and solidarity
- Family participation
- Family reciprocity
- Family cohesion

Society has accepted the transition period from a traditional set-up to a modern one. This means both conformity and modernity has their roots in the society and they have the negative or positive effects in both set-ups.

Social Capital Functional Rates of India

The term family as many social scientists and scholars had stated that it is an entire association. From the

functionalist perception family is an action and its consequence is evident in the society. So, researcher has perceived some facts related to the study and they are **the census rates of literacy of women in India** in the 1951 there had 8.9% then in the 1971 it raises to 22.0%, after that it increases in 1991 as 39.3% then in the next ten years i.e. 2001 their literacy rate again hiked of 53.7% followed by in 2011 it jumped to 64.6%. Hence, from 1951 to 2011 the census rates of literacy of women hiked year by year. As this fact is linked with the —Macro theory of Durkheim 'it states that calamity, dispute of social stratification and tensions were generated in the 19th century of the European Societies. The transition of old formation to new formations of beliefs was known to everybody his or her place was gone and the new ethical unique system has not been originated until now (Giddens, 1984:27)⁵. In the passing and passage society 'many roles and identity have changed but no new roles and identity could be found for the Women. Family identity were only enough for the women but with the passage of time, according to that it changed their sources of knowledge as well as, now in the time of modernization have new variety of social bases and credibility like degrees and employability.

As everybody knows that increasing education development can change the philosophy of human life also it provides with very new possibilities or opportunities; in the family generally we see that women demanded more voice especially in the household matters and as well as it is decline by someone who so ever want the dominance over them, and only through to education is the life itself can changes the life of the human, many changes seen into the family relationships and at last it leads to the ultimate compositional changes too.

Now in the recent time couples follow only new roles and bases and they are against the conventional or old values and it is called Theory of abnormality.

Secondly it is also visualized the fact from **the Census of India 1961; Paper no.1 of 1962 in the Female Work Participation**⁶ that in the year 1981 the rural area got 23.06% rate and in urban area it was 8.31% then again after 10 years there is an increment in the rate of female work participation in 1991 and so in the rural area it is 26.79% and in urban 9.19% and then again after 10 years the rate hiked in the year 2001 and was found to be 25.7% in the rural area and 11.9% in the urban area and the researcher finds that female work participation rate is rising slowly and hence it is progressive. It has lower rate in urban area than in rural area. So raising the rates in the rural areas is moderately high at the rate of 7.6% over in the upcoming 20 years. So researcher links the work participation rate to the “**Macro theory of Schelesky**” and states that the theory was grown in the Second World War done in the Germany where most of the family’s composition was totally demolished. The theory of Schelesky on justice of women and related to hike in career from all such aspects were above mentioned. In theory of Schelesky he believed that if working woman will go to outside then it will destroy the family composition and put it in danger of social relations in the family, so women cannot expertise and develop their children’s relations in that case. Schelesky highlights the point that relates to an improvement in the family relations and take out the dreadful pictures and also point out the dreadful effects of places from the family (Rosen Boum, 1988:23)⁷. Schelesky rejects some factors such as natural domination, role of society and the family enforce by the power which composes the family fragile and unbalanced and demolishes it. In the theory he considers the normal growth and development of the family are the vital aspects of family in the way of life. Family relationships have main basis to make family united and strong and as well as secure. He thinks that there must be some changes in the convention that may lead to volatility. Hence, in this way the conventional behaviors will be maintained and the family composition will be secured. In another words it possess power to tackle any problem and maintains

and secures the family solidity (Ibid: 33-36) in the Theory of family as a foundation.

Thirdly, researcher gives another fact increasing the divorce rate in India among the young married couples as according to a Hindustan Times through India facts collected on January 5, 2015 in Statistics⁸ which has been given below,

- In Mumbai, divorce cases filed in 2014 till November 30th, were 1,667(up from 5245 matters in 2010).
- In Kolkata, divorce cases filed in 2014 till November 30th, were 8347, there was a 350% raise the divorce cases in 2003 were 2,388.
- In the city of Lucknow, divorce cases filed in the family court in 2014 were about 2000.
- In Bengaluru, 3 more family courts were opened in 2013, to provide the demand of the three more family courts. They had 8,600 matters pending and 500 new cases were added every year.

So researcher will co-relate with the Macro theoretical perspective of —the theory of lessened disapproval of divorce: Giddens, Konic and etc. There are many aspects that influence divorce which have widely brought change in the lower and middle class families and that leads to many exceptions in the enrichment of the family. Today’s marriage proposals don’t favor the idea of dowry and don’t possess self-esteem. Today’s women are economically independent and they are not considered as the conventional ones who favored dowry, self-esteem and the economic cooperation. If people have more wealth and independent they become maladjusted and they can live their own life separately very easily as compared to the past because today’s people can have enough money to expense very easily and they don’t care and consider the need of others. This is a only the prime cause that in today’s modernization factor of divorce will not be approved and there consequences are above mentioned but

unhappily it increases with very high speed especially in the urban areas.

The study of UNICEF in 2008 declared that maternally those who are working and spending less time are giving birth of gambling into their children's growth. Study also demonstrates that if one of the children-sibling in the family found abnormal Behavior, therefore it has chances that the next of the siblings will also engage in the same abnormal behavior.

From India Human Development Survey 2004-2005 data taken from the empirical analyses⁹ revealed that 17% of the aged people stay along with their couples; just 2% stay solitary 85% aged people were stay in the co-resident among offspring. Modernization and industrialization also effects today's generations that gives rise to above factors or the bases of maladjustment of Social Capital as in a family relations. Therefore these bases children did not care their parents, and follow their own styles and patterns so these positions tends to move and make a gap between parents children so these are trends of today especially in the cities.

The above given factors of disorganization tends to decreases the social capital as well as decreases the adjustment between family relations or vice-versa, also producing distractions and differences between the husbands-wives with children's relationships.

Narratives of Urban Family

(a) Family Solidarity and Cohesion

1. Name: A, Age:-45 years, Gender: Female, (-ve response)

A is the female respondent, she has explained about her family after the interviewer has asked a question related to the parameter of family solidarity that how much you accept your spouse's beliefs? There A's has given a replied that her husband did not believed on her general family matters which she is normally

discussed or raise the family matter issues at home. She said that he has a negative influenced of his peer group society which has mainly affected the whole family members. I am a working woman and I have three children, mine husband are the habitual of having an alcohol along with his peer group, and when he come back he has not controlled over his tongue and using abusive language which shows a very wrong impact on her children also influenced the overall family development. Therefore I wanted to change my husband's habits as well as his behavior which is very horrible and harmful for the future of my children also if such kind of atmosphere will go on continue on my children, then they will follow or learn the disrespect, disobedience and one day they become made a valueless persons in the family because of his father's drinking habit has lost the overall attitude of the children and mislead the overall family. A's is also stated that my children are tried many times to understand him but there, they have not taken paid attention and therefore we have always received only hopeless. When my husband after having an alcohol then he has started to ruling out his misbehavior on the normal home discussions there he produced very clatter kind of sound their it represents the overall declination development towards the family. Our neighbors are stated that we know your husband's behavior we most of the time heard from him in a very high pitch tone or seen sometimes with brutal action over his family members.

2. Name: B, Age: 47 years, Gender: Female, (-ve response)

B is the head of the family member which she has disclosed about her family. Interviewer has asked a question from B that to what extent do you accept or support your spouse's decision on home affairs. There—B's has replied that I am working in a Private Company. There I have given 8 hours to my duty and takes 2 hours' time in everyday travelling. Thus Every day I have spent 10-11 hours from outside the home, there after I come back at home and I appealed to my husband on home affairs matter there is need of

support which is very necessary but he is not taken so much interest or even not accepted the decisions that implemented by me even he has started quarrel with me every day as he is not taking care of children also and neither he did not give any support in terms of financial. Actually the main reason behind these factors that my husband has engaged with some bad habits there he is working I knew such secret from one of his colleague through his that, he is indulged in some wrong or ill-mannered activities and her husband is spent his own income with one of the ex-woman, it means my husband have an extra marital affair as his colleague has stated all these matter therefore this is the only reason that my husband at home did not pay concentrate on his family members. He has produces a very terrible homely environment. Thereafter all situations we suffer a lot and felt so depressed, demotivated also we lose our confidence level. As my husband wanted to leave me and he also wanted to remarriage with that ex-woman though he has created such kind of irregular activities last so many months in the home.

(b) Familial Trust and Correlation

1. Name: K, Age: 43 years, Gender: Female, (-ve response)

K is the female respondent where she has told about her matrimonial family after asked by the interviewer that K has three children their two children are studying in Schools & one child is a college going. I am working in Private Company and I am an independent woman in the modern time of period or due to financial crisis though I am working. Then interviewer has asked a question from K's that how much trust do you have in your spouse's family? As it is the part of our research work or all chats should be in under confidential between the respondent and the interviewer only then after she listened this statement from an interviewer she become satisfied and replied to our question that everyday my spouse's family has created so many problems. I am working before my marriage to till at present date as I am belongs to a poor family and the elder daughter of my parents though I

was doing a job. Now some days later my husband's family's said that we did not like that you go outside the home, therefore they has created the distractions and disturbances among me and my spouse.—My spouse family misleads our conjugal relationship that, they have blamed on me that I have an affair with someone, that is the reason that she is working or she did not concentrate on her married life. They have created the very worst family environment or sometimes they tried to fight with me without any cause, their ill effects go to on my children and on their studies are also disturbed. My spouse's family has knitted many plans in their minds to break our conjugal relationship so they have produces the distractions in our relationship. My spouse did not support me because he is inclined towards his family members and due to all these happened increases the misunderstanding more and more in our life. However, I didn't trust on my spouse and his family members that they have generated the illogical sense of issues which is very unbearable or difficult to tolerate by me.

Narratives of Rural Family

(a) Family Solidarity and Cohesion

1. Name: C, Age:-50, Gender: Female (+ve response)
C is a female respondent; she is working in a Private Sector where she has always tried to give more time to her family. Interviewer has asked a question from the C's respondent that does your spouse respect you when you are at home. There she has replied that my spouse is a very supportive kind of a person, he has very good nature within the family members and with children also. She said that we have three sons their two got married, also they live together and one younger son is studying in the college. When my spouse has accomplishes good behavior or pay respects of mine hence their children has also observed or learn the lesson of respect from his father and they also get impressed or motivated from his father's behaviors. He is a very generous or a kind person also he spreads positivity around the family environment which makes the other family members mind's

balanced and positive. My spouse is very much against the unethical issues or disobedience kind of people though who have only one task to disturbed the whole environment so that their ill-manner behavior are automatically influenced the other family members also they learns the same from them. Now, after seen the positive homely environment our daughter-in-laws also feels very positive and happy, if we have seen the earlier behavior of my sons and my daughter-in-laws have both of them had very arrogant or short-tempered kind of behaviors but now they are at present they have lot of changes into their behaviors' when their biological parents of my daughter-in-laws have seen one day they felt very shocked after when they have seen the such kind of positive changes into their behaviors'; so they are the good and the positive sign of cohesiveness from which my children get inspired from their father.

2. Name: E, Age: 42, Gender: Male, (+ve response)

E is the head of the family. He is working in Private Limited Company in Noida. Interviewer has asked a question from E that to what extent do you accept or support your spouse's decision on home affairs. Then he has said that my spouse is a teacher and we have three children. He also said that when I come back from the duty he has given proper time with full attentiveness towards his family. His working hours is 9a.m to 6p.m. He told about her spouse that his wife is working in some private school there hours of working is from morning 7a.m to 2p.m, her working hours is quite very nice and good. He said that after she came back from the duty, she has managed all home affairs decision's as she has accepted or supported as well as give proper time with concentration with the children and after when they come back from their schools, their she asked about her children's daily routine and mainly she has focused on their studies, she make her children's daily time-table so that they can followed the daily routine according to that time table which have included their sports activity and exercises are also with their studies period of time. My spouse pays respect of mine in front of his family also she has

accepted or supported mine taken decisions on home affairs. Anybody can come from my family side, my wife serves a very great welcome of his family members and therefore, she has also received the great appreciation from them or she said that her husband understands the critical or the difficult circumstances which have come into the conjugal relationship though my husband's always support me as he is the best in all over the world. 'He said that his spouse has given proper time or support to his matrimonial family or even she has understands and make much balanced among the paternal family. She has giving the proper ethical values or even she taught my children or manage their all daily routine in an organized way, she is really such a very good teacher of home or as a Mother. From all above statements which I have presented our homely environment picture of which that I have mainly focused on the balanced home environment structure with good level of coordination among the husband-wife and children relationship. Our children have learned from us to acquire more good ethical values or coordination to develop their self-confidence or self-motivation. Though E's has said that I am very much satisfied from my spouse's behavior that she has deals her roles and responsibilities very nicely towards the family and she has performed the role of a mother very enthusiastically.

(b) Familial Trust and Correlation

1. Name: L, Age: 50 years, Gender: Male, (+ve response)

L is the male participant member of his family there he tells about his family that he is working in a Government Sector but for the job purposes I most of the time attended official trips, though it is very difficult for me to give proper time or attention to my family and my spouse is a non-working, we have four children, two are studying in school and two are studying in college. After known about the brief of L's family, then interviewer has asked a question from him that how much you have familial trust and co-relation within your family. L's has replied after heard about

the above given question by the interviewer, their respondent replied that our society have forcefully imposed to my spouse or my children like people from our society have negative thoughts to pressurize me and my wife like, that if your wife is educated then she should start some kind of work or do a job, or whenever I go outside for the job purposes tour then they have negatively started to provoke my wife but I said to them that it is our personal matter that whether she wanted to do a job or not after all, it is our personal matters. Society or relatives have most of the time interrupted and given unusual suggestions on our personal matters. Whenever I expressed about such an unusual comments or propaganda related to my spouse, and she felts so disappointed. Relatives or the people of society basically wanted to break down our husband-wife relationship so that they have produces the non-sense discussions on our personal matters or their main purpose is to divert our familial trust and co-relation also it is the daily routine of the people when I come back from the duty or sometimes come back from the official tour trip their I always heard about something new related to my family from them. My children and spouse having good familial composition and co-relation among the family members so we do trust towards each other. We both have good level of understanding also co-operates or balanced our conjugal life relationship in a positive manner. After so many negative planning have created by the side of relatives or the surrounding people's environment but at last we did not lose our confidence level. Also in the modern period of time there is a very high rate of inflation in financial terms but my spouse supports me. My spouse is a very helpful or a kind hearted person though she has managed or adjusted the home completely. My all children are very much matured by their minds and survive their each and every difficult situations of the life. So, I am very much glad to say that we are very much satisfied or happy from my family that they do trust and having good co-relation among the family members.

Conclusion

To conclude, it is difficult to pen-down the drastic changes under which Indian families are going. The system was never completely static of course, and slowly changes throughout the twentieth century. Until the end of the third decade of the twentieth century, however there was no political, social or industrial power that could successfully break Indian Families' self imposed isolation from the fourth decade of the twentieth century, particularly after the independence. We can say that changes are evidently from the traditional to transitional families which include the trends i.e. seen in the above mentioned empirical studies together of the following conclusions may be derived regarding the changes in family structure which also co-relates with social capital. The number of fissioned families is increasing , sons prefers to live separately from their parents whether it is job-related migration in the urban area, education, industrialization, adopt western values, modernization, effect of neo-local residence say: "that after marriage, children may live for some time with their parents but soon they prefer to live separately. With the continuous development of modernization and urbanization, the development is not limited to these fields only rather we get the evidences of development in family relations also, for, we find most of the young married couples opting and establishing a nuclear family being departed from their parental families. In the above given the study of Malipatil and Abrader Anshubhi have concluded that values are the core of the Social Capital which have exists trust, responsibility, family cohesion, family participation, understanding, reciprocity etc. are the values and these values are existed in the families but if these values are not present in the families it may cause that weakens the Family Social Capital and if they are present it may raise the growth of the family social capital. Therefore in the all above studies revealed that there have been seen the certain changes when weakens the Family Social Capital in the present Indian Society.

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